

RULE BOOK - ATP -

ALTERNATIVE TRANSIENT PROGRAM

RB-19E.PDF

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CAUE - COMITE ARGENTINO DE USUARIOS DE EMTP - ATP

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XIX-E. "OLD TO NEW ZNO" to update pre-"M39." ZnO data cards

Section II-A-23 explains access to this supporting program by means of an "OLD TO NEW ZNO" request. Only those with ZnO branch cards predating "M39." program versions of the spring and summer of 1984 need be concerned, of course. Old ZnO branch cards are easily recognized, since data is split into two or more isolated groups. A Type-92 nonlinear element just reserved space for the ZnO arrester, and it involved a dummy characteristic. Parameters of the ZnO itself were read from special data cards immediately before the output-variable (usually node-voltage) specification cards of Section XII.

The "OLD TO NEW ZNO" special request is to be followed by the complete, old data case. The conversion routine deals with variable classes, counting blank cards that terminate these, so be careful if other than a complete data case is supplied. As an illustration, consider the 2nd subcase of BENCHMARK DC-14. There is no printout at all while the program is executing, except for any comment cards. When the ZnO data conversion is complete, there will be a one-line message to this effect, as shown by the following output:

```

C          1          2          3          4          5          6          7
C 3456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456
C -----|-----
Request to convert old ZnO data to new formats. | OLD TO NEW ZNO      { Spe
Done with ZnO conversion in "SATURA" of overlay 24.
Timing figures characterizing central processor (CP) solution speed. -----

```

It is the user's responsibility to pick up the punched cards (via \$PUNCH request), since otherwise, there is no output.

XIX-F. DATA BASE MODULE

IX-F-1. PURPOSE AND APPLICATIONS

Already in 1983, EMTF enhancements were made to allow the user to modularize network sections. Any repetitive connection of certain network elements can be seen as such a module. The more a certain grouping of network elements is repeated through the network, the more efficient the usage of modules will be.

The network section within the module is fully described in what is called a template. This template uses fixed values in combination with module arguments, pretty much in the same format as a normal network would be represented for EMTF purposes. Details on both argument definitions and creation of templates will be discussed further in this section.

Such module can have fixed values in combination with variables or arguments, referring to both numerical values and node names. For numerical data, some of the parameters in such module can have fixed values, whereas other values should be treated as parameters. Parameter values will be allocated when referring to the module in question. This is done by the extended and powerful \$INCLUDE command. On the other hand, node names always should have unique names throughout the network under study. This can be obtained either by user allocation (extended \$INCLUDE command), either by automatic name generation (treatment of dummy node names).

Possible examples of usage of such modules :

- generator, followed by subtransient reactance. The connecting names of this module with the rest of the network under simulation should be under user control. Internal node names could receive an automatically generated node name. The value of the subtransient reactance can be either fixed or treated as a parameter.
- frequency-dependent cable- or overhead line models (JMARTI or SEMLYEN models). In this case, one can assume fixed values for the actual fitting parameters. But node names, which are the connection between the model and the rest of the network under study, better can be declared as arguments of the module.
- The usage of "nested" includes is possible, too. The situation of a modularized substation, including a module containing generator and subtransient reactance and another module taking the transformer and busbars into account is a typical example using the feature of "nested includes".

After a while, one will end with a lot of modules. Then it will become difficult to have an overview of all existing models. Further it will become difficult to remember the meaning and the number of arguments per module. Most of these problems can be handled by using strong standardisation in module naming. Further, usage of a relational data base (such as DBASE III) would be useful.

The input format for the supporting routine "DATA BASE MODULE" contains two different sections:

- an "argument declaration list"
- a "template"

"Arguments" are parameter names. There are three types of arguments:

- named arguments referring to node names;
- named arguments referring to numerical values;
- dummy arguments (should always refer to internal node names of the module).

The "argument declaration list" defines whether an argument is named or dummy. For named arguments, further specification is needed in order to make the difference between node name parameters or numerical parameters. Hence the named arguments are treated different from the dummy arguments. Both will be discussed separately.

The *named arguments* will have a value allocated through the \$INCLUDE argument list (sections I-D-19 and I-K). Currently, the number of named arguments in such list is limited to 35. The named arguments can be defined in any arbitrary order and a mixed sequence of node name arguments and numerical arguments is allowed. But the sequence of arguments in the argument declaration list of the template should correspond to the sequence of allocated values and node names in the \$INCLUDE argument list. Further, it is the user's responsibility to guarantee the uniqueness of node names throughout the entire network under simulation. This is rather easy to obtain for connection points but it becomes extremely cumbersome for internal node names within the module. For internal node names (i.e. nodes inside the module, without any link to the rest of the network), the feature of "dummy arguments" can assist the user in obtaining unique node names all over the network under study.

The allocation of names to *dummy arguments* is fully automatized, so that the number of dummy arguments basically is without any limit. The generation procedure for naming is based on a user defined 3-digit root name, followed by a three-digit serialization number. So at first glance the number of dummy arguments is limited to 1.000. But via the \$DUMMY command, the user is able to modify the three-digit root name to another string. Just as the named arguments, the dummy arguments need to be specified in the argument declaration list, in any arbitrary order. But unlike the named arguments, the dummy arguments don't need to have a value allocated in the \$INCLUDE argument list since as explained before, dummy arguments will receive a serialized name automatically.

A "template" is nothing else then the EMTP input representation of the module or network section under study. Hence all rules applicable to the normal EMTP input format are also applicable to this templates. The only difference is that in some places, arguments (parameter names) rather than actual values are used. This means that there is a combined use of both actual values and arguments. Further, the "/" card" feature is in use (see section I-J: EMTP data sorting by class).

Let's discuss the input rules in more detail now.

IX-F-2. INPUT DATA-DECK STRUCTURE

The input file for the supporting routine "DATA BASE MODULE" should show following card sequence:

1. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE --NOSORT--
2. DATA BASE MODULE request card
3. SERASE card
4. argument declaration list

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- (ARG, NUM, DUM)
5. template
(/BRANCH, /SWITCH, /SOURCE,)
 6. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE special request card
 7. Comment card
 8. \$PUNCH card
 9. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE special request card
 10. BLANK card terminating all cases

Let's discuss the input cards one by one now, in more detail:

1. "BEGIN NEW DATA CASE" special request card, specifying the NOSORT option, somewhere on the very first input card (the position of the word NOSORT is unimportant). This card is always used to indicate the beginning of a new program run. Hence this special request card can be thought of as a case separation marker.
2. "DATA BASE MODULE" request card. This special-request card transfers program control to the supporting routine that searches the user's raw data for the character strings of all arguments of interest and establishes numerical pointers for all arguments in order to speed up later usage with the empowered \$INCLUDE command, allowing the transfer of arguments (see sections I-D-19 and I-K).
3. \$ERASE card. This card is used to clear the buffer that holds punched card output (see section I-D-17).
4. Argument declaration list (ARG, NUM, DUM). The argument declaration list defines whether an argument is named or dummy. For named arguments, further specification is needed in order to make the difference between node name parameters or numerical parameters. Let's discuss the declaration of all three argument types separately:

- 4a. *Named arguments referring to node names.*
Declaration (free format):

ARG name1, name2, ...

Remarks :

- The sequence in this argument list later should correspond to the sequence of allocated values in the \$INCLUDE argument list.
- In order to avoid a "length mismatch error", the length of the argument name must be equal to the length of the allocated name specified in the \$INCLUDE argument list. In order to adjust the argument length, following symbols can be used:
 - "_" (underscore) in the argument name
 - "#" (pound sign) in the allocated name
- Automatic phase indication is possible too. In that case, only the first five digits of the name field are free for parametric usage. The sixth (utmost right) digit remains fixed in the template (see point 5, further in this section)

4b. *Named arguments referring to numerical values.*

Declaration (free-format):

```
ARG name1, value1, value2, ...
NUM value1, value2
```

Remarks:

- The sequence in this argument list later should correspond to the sequence of allocated values in the \$INCLUDE argument list. Further, all named arguments referring to numerical values should likewise be declared in a NUM-list. The order of arguments in the NUM-list is of no importance, however.
- In order to avoid a "length mismatch error", the length of the argument name must be larger than (or equal to) the length of the allocated value specified in the \$INCLUDE argument list. In order to adjust the argument length, following symbol can be used:
"_" (underscore) in the argument name
- With respect to the E-format usage for reals, it is advised to use real numbers with decimal point in the \$INCLUDE argument list.

4c. *Dummy arguments should always refer to internal node names of the module.*

Declaration (free-format):

```
ARG name1, value1, ....
NUM value1, ...
DUM dummy1, dummy2, ....
```

Remark:

- Dummy argument names DON'T appear in the ARG-list, nor the NUM-list. Consequently no value will be allocated via the \$INCLUDE argument list.
- The sequence of dummy names in the DUM-declaration list is purely arbitrary. The name allocation will be generated automatically, based upon a three-digit root name, followed by a unique three-digit serialization number.
- In order to avoid a "length mismatch error", it is important that the argument name contains six digits. In order to adjust the argument length, following symbol can be used:
"_" (underscore) in the argument name

5. Template (/BRANCH, /SWITCH, /SOURCE,).

A "template" is nothing else than the EMTP input representation of the module or network section under study. Hence all rules applicable to the normal EMTP input format are also applicable to this template. The only difference is that in some places, arguments (parameter names) rather than actual values are used. Further, the "/" card feature is in use (see section I-J: EMTP data sorting by class). Arguments should be carefully placed in the template, though:

5a. *Named arguments referring to node names.*

In the template, arguments referring to node names should be placed left-adjusted in the zone reserved for such variables in normal EMTP input cards. It is important to remark that the allocated node names will be left-adjusted in the zone defined by the argument name in the template.

Automatic phase indication is possible too. In that case, only the first five digits of the name field are free for parametric usage. The sixth (utmost right) digit remains fixed in the template.

5b. *Named arguments referring to numerical values.*

In the template, arguments referring to numerical values should be placed right-adjusted in the zone reserved for such variables in normal EMTP input cards. It is important to remark that the allocated value will be right-adjusted in the zone defined by the argument name in the template. With respect to the E-format usage for reals, it is advised to use real numbers with decimal point in the \$INCLUDE argument list.

5c. *Dummy arguments, always referring to internal node names of the module.*

In the template, dummy arguments referring to node names should be placed in the zone reserved for such variables in normal EMTP input cards. Since by definition, the length of argument name and allocated name are both equal to six, the positioning of names remains unchanged.

6. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE.

7. Comment card.

This combined case separation marker is used as a flag, indicating that the data card input for the modularization is terminated here. The number of comment cards needed is controlled by variable KASEND in the "startup" file.

8. \$PUNCH card.

This special request command is used to flush the contents of the punch buffer, which now contains numerical pointers for all arguments used in the template, as well as the template itself.

The usage of these pointers will speed up later processing of the template via the empowered \$INCLUDE command (see section I-D-19), certainly when actual values and names should be allocated to the arguments .

9. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE special request card.

This card is always used as a case separation marker.

10. BLANK card terminating all cases.

IX-F-3. EXAMPLE

Benchmarks documenting this usage are: DC36 (template creation) and DC8 (usage of the created punch file). Nested usage is explained in DC58. The best way to discuss the possibilities of this powerfull tool is to illustrate its usage for a simple example, which represents a 6-valve thyristor bridge used in HVDC stations. The electrical scheme of this circuit is represented in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Schematic diagram of the HVDC bridge represented in the template
 Arguments : NODE, MINUS, PLUS, FIRE, RESIS, CAPACI
 Dummy : MID1, MID2, MID3, MID4, MID5, MID6

a) Following file is an example of the corresponding input needed for the DATA BASE MODULE supporting routine.

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE          ---- NOSORT ----
DATA BASE MODULE
SERASE
ARG. _NODE, _MINUS, _PLUS, _FIRE, RESIS, CAPACI
NUM, RESIS, CAPACI
DUM. _MID1, _MID2, _MID3, _MID4, _MID5, _MID6
/BRANCH
C3 Begin with anode reactors and parallel resistors (6 pairs):
  _NODEA _MID1          RESIS    CAPACI
  _NODEA _MID1          RESIS    1.0
  _NODEB _MID3          RESIS
  _NODEB _MID3          RESIS    1.0
  _NODEC _MID5          RESIS
  _NODEC _MID5          RESIS    1.0
  _PLUS  _MID4          RESIS
  _PLUS  _MID4          RESIS    1.0
  _PLUS  _MID6          RESIS
  _PLUS  _MID6          RESIS    1.0
  _PLUS  _MID2          RESIS
  _PLUS  _MID2          RESIS    1.0
C3 Next come the snubber circuits, across valves and anode reactors:
  _NODEA _MINUS        1200.    0.1
  _NODEB _MINUS        1200.    0.1
  _NODEC _MINUS        1200.    0.1
  _NODEA _PLUS         1200.    0.1
  _NODEB _PLUS         1200.    0.1
  _NODEC _PLUS         1200.    0.1
C3 Next come the valves:
/SWITCH
11 _MID1 _MINUS          _FIRE2
11 _MID3 _MINUS          _FIRE4
11 _MID5 _MINUS          _FIRE6
11 _MID4 _NODEA          _FIRE5
11 _MID6 _NODEB          _FIRE1
11 _MID2 _NODEC          _FIRE3
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
C Just a comment card
SPUNCH ( Flush critical portion of answers from preceding first subcase
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
BLANK
  
```

When inspecting this file, please note the following:

- BEGIN NEW DATA CASE ; free-format NOSORT - declaratie !!
- \$ERASE card to flush the punch buffer.
- Automatic phase indication in the template; "_NODE" is only 5 digits long, but in the template, the node names are "_NODEA", "_NODEB", "_NODEC", etc. In these names, only the first 5 digits are variable, the last digit (phase indicator) is fixed. The same remark applies for "_FIRE", used in names "_FIRE1", "_FIRE2", etc. Remark that dummy names never can have automatic phase indication.
- Because "__MID1", "__MID2", etc. are internal node names (i.e. without any connection toward the outside of the module) they could be declared as dummy argument. But in this case, the length of the argument name must be set equal to 6. Hence note the use of "_" (underscore).
- Arguments referring to node names (be it named or dummy) are always positioned left-adjusted in the template; _NODE, _MINUS, __PLUS, _FIRE, __MID1, __MID2, __MID3, __MID4, __MID5, __MID6.
- Arguments referring to numerical values are positioned right-adjusted in the template; RESIS, CAPACI.
- Some of the parameters have fixed values, whereas other numerical values get their value allocated through a named argument; RESIS, CAPACI.
- Only one comment card needed, since KASEND = 1 in the startup file used here.

b) Following is an extract of the output of supporting routine "DATA BASE MODULE":

:
A listing of 80-column card images now being flushed from punch buffer follows.

```

.....
123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789
.....
KARD  2  2  2  2  3  3  4  4  4  5  5  6  6  6  7  7  8  8  8  9  9 10 10 11
      11 12 12 12 13 13 14 14 15 15 16 16 17 17 18 18 19 19 21 21 22 22 22 23
      23 23 24 24 24 25 25 25 26 26 26
KARG  1  5  6 -1  1 -1  1  5 -3  1 -3  1  5 -5  1 -5  3  5 -4  3 -4  3  5 -6  3
      -6  3  5 -2  3 -2  1  2  1  2  1  2  1  3  1  3  1  3  2  4 -1  2  4 -3  2
      4 -5  1  4 -4  1  4 -6  1  4 -2
KBEG  3 28 39  9  3  9  3 28  9  3  9  3 28  9  3  9  3 28  9  3  9  3 28  9  3
      9  3 28  9  3  9  3  9  3  9  3  9  3  9  3  9  3  9  65  3  9  65  3  9
      65  3  9  65  3  9  65  3  9  65  3
KEND  7 32 44 14  7 14  7 32 14  7 14  7 32 14  7 14  8 32 14  8 14  8 32 14  8
      14  8 32 14  8 14  7 14  7 14  7 14  7 14  7 14  7 14 14 69  8 14 69  8 14
      69  8 13 69  8 13 69  8 13 69  8
KTEX  1  0  0  1  1  1  1  0  1  1  1  1  0  1  1  1  1  0  1  1  1  1  0  1  1
      1  1  0  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1
      1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1  1

```

```

/BRANCH
C3 BEGIN WITH ANODE REACTORS AND PARALLEL RESISTORS (6 PAIRS):
  _NODEA __MID1          RESIS          CAPACI
:
:
11 __MID2 NODEC          FIRE3
SEOF  User-supplied header cards follow.      12-Sep-88 14.33.22
ARG.  _NODE  _MINUS.  __PLUS.  _FIRE.RESIS.CAPACI
NUM. RESIS.CAPACI
DUM.  __MID1. __MID2. __MID3. __MID4. __MID5. __MID6
***** End of LUNIT7 punched cards as flushed by SPUNCH request *****

```

Remark that besides the entire template, the punch buffer now contains numerical pointers for all arguments used in the template. Lets discuss the meaning of all five these pointing vectors:

- KARD : This can be thought of as the record number of the template. Remark that some card numbers (e.g. 1, 20, ...) seem to be missing. In effect, these card numbers refer to so-called "/"-cards (e.g. card 1=/branch, card 20=/switch, etc).
- KARG : Named arguments have a positive value for KARG, whereas dummy arguments show negative KARG-values. Positive KARG values refer to the position of the current argument name in the ARG declaration list, whereas negative KARG values refer to the position of the current argument name in the DUM declaration list.
- KBEG : First position, taken by the current argument name on the specified card in the template.
- KEND : Last position, taken by the current argument name on the specified card in the template.
- KTEX : Flag, indicating whether the specified argument refers to a numeric value (0) or a node name (1).

Once created, it is important NOT to though the created punch file again. Even simple insertion of comment lines would ruin the pointer setup.

c) Next data set illustrates how this module named \WSM/PONSK.PCH then should be used in network simulations:

Fig.2: Allocation of argument values (compare with Fig.1)

DUM-list	ARG-list
MID1 = XYZ520	NODE = ACNOD
MID2 = XYZ521	FIRE = FIRE
MID3 = XYZ522	MINUS = MINUS
MID4 = XYZ523	PLUS = PLUS
MID5 = XYZ524	RESIS = 5000.
MID6 = XYZ525	CAPACI = 3.

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
SPREFIX, \WSM/
SSUFFIX, .PCH
      .005      4.0
      1      -1      1      1      -1
      5      5      20      20
TACS HYBRID
99 FIRE1 = TIMEX
99 FIRE2 = TIMEX
99 FIRE3 = TIMEX
13FAKE
98 FIRE452+UNITY      1.      0.      0.      TIMEX
98 FIRE552+UNITY      1.      0.      0.      TIMEX
98 FIRE652+UNITY      1.      0.      0.      TIMEX
BLANK card ends all TACS data
C
C Here the root name is set to XYZ and the offset is set to 519, so the numbering of the
C dummy node names starts at number 520.
C
SDUMMY, XYZ519
C
C By means of the following $INCLUDE request, the routine PONSX.PCH is included
C For the extension "PCH", the command SSUFFIX was issued in the beginning of this program.
C
$INCLUDE, PONSX, ACNOD, #MINUS, ##PLUS, #FIRE, 5000., 3.0
BLANK card ending BRANCH cards
BLANK card ending SWITCH cards
:
:

```

When inspecting this file, please note the following:

- SPREFIX and SSUFFIX cards are used to set the working directory and default extension of the file name to be included. Remark that the sequence:


```

SPREFIX, \WSM/
SSUFFIX, .PCH
$INCLUDE, PONSX, ACNOD, #MINUS, ##PLUS, #FIRE, 5000., 3.0

```

 would be equivalent with following sequence:


```

$INCLUDE, \WSM/PONSX.PCH, ACNOD, #MINUS, ##PLUS, #FIRE, 5000., 3.0

```
 - The \$INCLUDE option internally will be interpreted as the dynamic opening of the specified file, and then replace the arguments by their actual values or names (see sections I-D-19 and I-K). Hence this feature only works on those computers and/or operating systems that allow dynamic file opening. Contact program maintenance if there is doubt about this possibilities for your computer system and/or possibilities to emulate this feature. In our example, this allocation will have following consequences (order specified in the ARG-list):


```

ARG,      _NODE, _MINUS, _PLUS, _FIRE, RESIS, CAPACI
$INCLUDE, filename, ACNOD, #MINUS, ##PLUS, #FIRE, 5000., 3.

```
 - Note the sequence as well as the length of the allocated values. Both should agree with the the argument specifications in the input file for the DATA BASE MODULE supporting routine.
 - The \$DUMMY card can be used to reset both the root name and the initial serialization number for dummy node names. In our example, this will have following consequences (order specified in the DUM-list):


```

SDUMMY, XYZ519
DUM,      _MID1, _MID2, _MID3, _MID4, _MID5, _MID6
node names: XYZ520, XYZ521, XYZ522, XYZ523, XYZ524, XYZ525

```
- d) Finally, an extract of the output of the resulting transient simulation will be printed (see Fig.2).

Done with disk file (CLOSE). J. N19 = 57 3998
 Done copying lower cards back to top (DO 1835).
 (----) Done with "-"-card sorting by data class. Remember that the source file appears different from interpreted input data.
 Alternative Transients Program (ATP). Apollo translation. Copyright 1984. Use licensed only through LEC (K.U. Leuven, Belgium).
 Date (dd-mth-yy) and time of day (hh:mm:ss) = 12-Sep-88 14.30.18 Name of the disk plot file, if any, is: PLOTYYmmddhhmmss.P14
 For information, consult the copyrighted ATP EMTF Rule Book published by LEC in July, 1987. Last major program update: May, 1988
 Total length of "LABCOM" tables = 59770 (INTEGER words). "VARDIM" List Sizes follow: 214 255 425 42 2125
 34 595 1487 63 136 42 50 4250 17 700 34 3 4 1600 660 100 150 3400 3 400 42 42

Descriptive interpretation of input data cards. Input data card images are shown below, all 80 columns, character by character
 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
 01234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890

<p>Comment card. NUMDCD = 1. Marker card preceding new EMTF data case. Comment card. NUMDCD = 5. Comment card. NUMDCD = 7. Comment card. NUMDCD = 8. Misc. data. 5.000E-03 4.000E+00 0.000E+00 Misc. data. 1 -1 1 1 1 -1 0 0 0 0 Printout: 5 5 20 20 0 0 Electric network, too. But TACS data first ... Free-format TACS supplemental variable defined. Free-format TACS supplemental variable defined. Free-format TACS supplemental variable defined. TACS source. 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 TACS supplemental device type 52. TACS supplemental device type 52. TACS supplemental device type 52. Blank card terminating all TACS data cards. Comment card. NUMDCD = 22. Comment card. NUMDCD = 23. Comment card. NUMDCD = 24. Comment card. NUMDCD = 25. Comment card. NUMDCD = 26. Comment card. NUMDCD = 27. Comment card. NUMDCD = 28. Comment card. NUMDCD = 29. Comment card. NUMDCD = 30. Comment card. NUMDCD = 31. Series R-L-C. 5.000E+03 0.000E+00 3.000E-06 Series R-L-C. 0.000E+00 1.000E-03 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 5.000E+03 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 0.000E+00 1.000E-03 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 5.000E+03 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 0.000E+00 1.000E-03 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 5.000E+03 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 0.000E+00 1.000E-03 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 5.000E+03 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 0.000E+00 1.000E-03 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 5.000E+03 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 0.000E+00 1.000E-03 0.000E+00 Series R-L-C. 1.200E+03 0.000E+00 1.000E-07 Blank card ending branches. (NR. NTOT = 18 12) Valve. 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 " FIRE2" Valve. 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 " FIRE4" Valve. 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 " FIRE6" Valve. 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 " FIRE5" Valve. 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 " FIRE1" Valve. 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 0.000E+00 " FIRE3" Blank card ending switches. KSWTCH = 6.</p>	<p>C date:GEBRUIX.DAT BEGIN NEW DATA CASE C C SPREFIX. \WSM/ C SSUFFIX. .PCB .005 4.0 1 -1 1 1 1 -1 5 5 20 20 TACS HYBRID 99 FIRE1 = TIMEX 99 FIRE2 = TIMEX 99 FIRE3 = TIMEX 13FAKE 98 FIRE452=UNITY 1. 0. 0. TIMEX 98 FIRE552=UNITY 1. 0. 0. TIMEX 98 FIRE652=UNITY 1. 0. 0. TIMEX BLANK card ends all TACS data C C Here the root name is set to XYZ and the offset is set to 519, so the number in C dummy node names starts at number 520. C C SDUPPLY ,XYZ519 C C By means of the following \$INCLUDE request, the routine POWSK.PCB is included C For the extension "PCB", the command \$SUFFIX was issued in the beginning of th C C \$INCLUDE, POWSK, ACNOD, #MINUS, ##PLUS, #FIRE, 5000., 3.0 ACNODAKY2520 5000. 3.0 ACNODAKY2520 1.0 ACNODBKX2522 5000. ACNODBKX2522 1.0 ACNODCKY2524 5000. ACNODCKY2524 1.0 PLUSKY2523 5000. PLUSKY2523 1.0 PLUSKY2525 5000. PLUSKY2525 1.0 PLUSKY2521 5000. PLUSKY2521 1.0 ACNODA MINUS 1200. 0.1 ACNODB MINUS 1200. 0.1 ACNODC MINUS 1200. 0.1 ACYODA PLUS 1200. 0.1 ACNODB PLUS 1200. 0.1 ACNODC PLUS 1200. 0.1 BLANK card ending BRANCH cards 11XY2520 MINUS FIRE2 11XY2522 MINUS FIRE4 11XY2524 MINUS FIRE6 11XY2523ACNODA FIRE5 11XY2525ACNODB FIRE1 11XY2521ACNODC FIRE3 BLANK card ending SWITCH cards</p>
--	---

When inspecting this output, please note the following:

- Node names are left-justified in their field, whereas numerical values are right-justified in the field specified by the argument name in the template.
- All cards are sorted and put under the section they belong; branches are added to the branch card group, switches to the switch card group and sources to the source card group. All values (named as well as dummy arguments) are allocated as was pre-defined in the template and argument list.

XIX-G "SATURA" TO DERIVE (ψ,i) PEAKVALUE CURVES

XIX-G-1. Purpose & Applications

The specification of nonlinear inductors requires a (flux-current) saturation curve relating the total flux linkage to the element current. Such curve can be derived, either by using RMS (voltage, current) readings, or by using a (current, incremental inductance) characteristic.

Both approaches are possible, and will be discussed separately, because of the differences in data entry.

The punched results (ψ,i) then can be used in the saturable transformer component model (section IV-E) or in the nonlinear inductor (type-98 pseudo-nonlinear reactor or type-93 nonlinear inductance) that can be added externally to linear transformer models obtained via BCTRAN (section XIX-C) or XFORMER (section XIX-A).

Although the resulting saturation curve will be single-valued, hysteresis can be taken into account by manual displacement of the values of the current. These results then can be used for the type-96 pseudo-nonlinear hysteric reactor (section V-D). This solution is an alternative for the special supporting routine HYSDAT (section XIX-H).

XIX-G-2. Input data deck structure for SATURA

In general, an input data-deck for the supporting routine SATURA has the following structure:

1. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
2. SATURA - special request to activate supporting routine SATURA (see section II-A-
3. \$ERASE - request (optional) to clear punch buffer
4. Per unit base specification card
5. Card grouping, supplying (I_{RMS} , V_{RMS}) or (current, incremental inductance) break points, terminated by a special flag card
6. \$PUNCH - request (optional) to activate punching

Remark that the points 3 through 6 may be repeated as many times as desired. Each such grouping then is considered as a separate data case, corresponding to a different saturation curve.

7. BLANK CARD ending all saturation cases
8. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
9. BLANK CARD ending all cases

For an example of such input, the reader is referred to benchmark DC13 (first subcase) or to section XIX-G-3. Because of the possibility of two different approaches, two different data entries will be discussed next:

- (I_{RMS} , V_{RMS}) data entry;
- (I , L) data entry.

Only card type 4 and 5 will be discussed. All other cards are self-explanatory.

XIX-G-2.a. (I_{RMS} , V_{RMS}) data entry

Fig.1: (I_{RMS} , V_{RMS}) curve, specified by break points

With an impressed sinusoidal voltage, an RMS reading of the non-sinusoidal current into the winding is obtained. Supporting program "SATURA" is designed to convert from the user's RMS ($v-i$) curve to the peak values of a ($\psi-i$) curve needed for transient simulation.

The user inputs his ($v-i$) curve (RMS values) as a sequence of points, with linear interpolation between these values assumed. The output ($\psi-i$) curve (peak values) is likewise piecewise-linear with the same number of points. Following approximations are made:

1. The use of linear interpolation in between points.
2. The use of finite-difference approximation to sinusoidal excitation. One-degree step-size is used, along with trapezoidal-rule integration where needed.
3. Hysteresis is ignored.

Let us discuss the data entry in more detail now. Only card type 4 and 5 will be discussed here.

Card 4. The card format for the per unit base specification card :

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
FREQ	VBASE	SBASE	IPUNCH	KTHIRD			
E8.0	E8.0	E8.0	8	8			

Parameters:

- FREQ: frequency (in Hz) of the impressed sinusoidal voltage source.
- VBASE: single-phase base voltage (in kV) on which the input break points are based.
- SBASE: single-phase base power (in MVA) on which the input break points are based.
- IPUNCH: parameter controlling the punched card output of the derived (flux-current) characteristic.
 - = 0 : no curve will be punched;
 - = 1 : curve will be punched, provided the \$PUNCH card is being specified (see card 6).
 The cards will be punched, one breakpoint per card, using the 2E16.8 format, immediately usable for all applications.
- KTHIRD: parameter controlling the type of output.
 - = 0 : only first-quadrant output;
 - = 1 : full curve (first- and third-quadrant output).

Card 5. Next comes a card grouping, supplying the (I_{RMS} , V_{RMS}) break points :

Only one breakpoint per card can be specified. One should start by specifying the break point closest to the origin (omitting point (0, 0), though), and then moving continuously away. The curve must be single-valued. Successive slopes should be non-decreasing. The slope defined by the last breakpoint will be extrapolated to infinity (cfr. fig. 1). Values are in per unit, based on the previously-specified single-phase base :

$$I_{base} = \frac{S_{base}}{V_{base}} (kA)$$

$$I_{RMS}(pu) = I_{RMS}(A) / I_{base}(A)$$

$$V_{RMS}(pu) = V_{RMS}(kV) / V_{base}(kV)$$

The card format to be used is as follows :

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
I _{RMS} [P.U.]				V _{RMS} [P.U.]			
E16.0				E16.0			

- The maximum number of breakpoints is limited to 100.
- If the saturation curve is intended for a type-98 pseudo-nonlinear element, a maximum of five breakpoints is recommended, in order to avoid numerical tracking problems.
- On the other hand, for a type-93 true nonlinear element, many breakpoints around the kneepoint of the saturation curve should be used whenever a smooth approximation of the nonlinear magnetizing current is of interest.

This card grouping should be terminated by following special flag card :

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
9999							

XIX-G-2.b. (I, L) data entry

Instead of an (I_{RMS}, V_{RMS}) characteristic, the user has the option of inputting a current versus incremental inductance characteristic. The trapezoidal rule of integration is then used in this case, to convert the inductance curve into the desired output curve of flux versus current :

$$\psi(i) = \int_0^i L(n)dn \quad \psi_1 = 0$$

$$\psi_k = \psi_{k-1} + \left\{ \frac{L_k + L_{k-1}}{2} \right\} \cdot (i_k - i_{k-1}) \quad k = 2, 3, \dots$$

Fig. 2: Current versus incremental inductance characteristic

Card 4. The card format for the per unit base specification :

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
FLAG	SCALI	SCALL	IPUNCH	KTHIRD			
E8.0	E8.0	E8.0	8	8			

Parameters:

FLAG: = -1; special request flag for (I,L) data entry (as opposed to (I_{RMS}, V_{RMS}) data entry, explained in point 2.a).

SCALI: multiplier for the current coordinate of the input breakpoint, in order to obtain results in Amps.

SCALL: multiplier for the inductance coordinate of the input breakpoint, in order to obtain results in Henries.

Note: If both SCALI and SCALL are blank or zero, the supplied characteristic is understood being specified in units of Amps and Henries, so that no conversion is necessary.

IPUNCH: see point 2.a.

KTHIRD: see point 2.a.

Note: Although for the (I,L) data entry, the origin point (0, 0) of the saturation curve appears in the printed output, this value will be omitted in the punched output.

Card 5. Card grouping specifying a current versus an incremental inductance characteristic.

The current breakpoints i_k must be monotone increasing, starting with value zero. Values are in Amps (if SCALI = 0) or otherwise, $i_k * SCALI$ is in Amps. The incremental inductance values $L_k = \left[\frac{d\psi}{di} \right]_{i_k}$ all must be positive. Values are in Henries (if SCALL = 0) or otherwise, $L_k * SCALL$ is in Henries.

The card format to be used is as follows :

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
L _k				L _k			
E16.0				E16.0			

The same recommendations as in point 2.a. are valid. This card grouping should be terminated by the same special flag card, as explained in 2.a.

XIX-G-3. 3. Example

Consider a five-leg core-type transformer with STAR-connected high-voltage winding with grounded neutral and DELTA-connected low voltage winding (YNd5).

Rated power: 750 MVA
 Rated voltage: 420 kV/27 kV (line-line values)

From the positive-sequence excitation test, following data are available :

Table 1.

U _{ex}	I _{ex}	P _{ex}
KV	A	KW
22.76	8.20	206.21
24.29	11.35	240.26
25.64	15.50	270.13
27.00	21.16	311.00
27.50	24.68	323.03
28.47	31.63	355.48
29.10	38.30	385.41
32.50	80.97	560.00

where U_{ex} = excitation voltage (RMS, line-line value)
 I_{ex} = excitation current (RMS, three-phase average)
 P_{ex} = excitation loss (three-phase value)

As a first approximation, the RMS excitation current I_{ex,w} in a DELTA winding equals

$$I_{ex,w} = I_{ex} / \sqrt{3} \text{ (harmonics neglected)}$$

Further, the RMS magnetizing current I_{m,w} in the DELTA winding is approximated by

$$I_{m,w} = \sqrt{I_{ex,w}^2 - \left(\frac{P_{ex}}{3U_{ex}}\right)^2}$$

Hence, the above measured Table 1 reduces to following saturation characteristic :

Table 2:

U _{ex}	I _{rw}
KV	A
22.76	3.65
24.29	5.66
25.64	8.23
27.00	11.60
27.50	13.70
28.47	17.78
29.10	21.66
32.50	46.40

When converting this characteristic into input data for supporting routine SATURA, we first need to convert to per unit values for the equivalent phase.

$$S_{base} = 750/3 = 250 \text{ MVA}$$

$$V_{base} = 27 \text{ kV}$$

$$I_{base} = \frac{750}{\sqrt{3} \times 27} = 9259 \text{ A}$$

The input data (table 3) can be obtained from table 2, using the following conversion formulas :

$$I_{RMS}(pu) = I_{RMS}(A) / I_{base}(A)$$

$$V_{RMS}(pu) = V_{RMS}(kV) / V_{base}(kV)$$

This finally results in following table :

Table 3:

V _{RMS} (pu)	I _{RMS} (pu)
0.8430	0.3942 E-3
0.8996	0.6113 E-3
0.9496	0.8888 E-3
1.000	1.253 E-3
1.019	1.480 E-3
1.054	1.920 E-3
1.078	2.333 E-3
1.204	5.011 E-3

The input file for supporting routine SATURA then looks as follows:

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
C input data for supporting routine SATURA
C Excitation test results for 3-phase transformer
C     UBASE = 27 kv (RMS, equivalent phase)
C     SBASE = 750/3 = 250 MVA (equivalent phase)
C     Ibase = 250 / 27 = 9.26 kA
C
C 34567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890
C      1      2      3      4      5      6      7      8
SERASE
SATURATION
50.0  27.00  250.0      1      0
.3942      -3 .8430
    
```

```
.6113      -3 .8996
.8888      -3 .9496
1.253      -3 1.0
1.480      -3 1.019
1.920      -3 1.054
2.333      -3 1.078
5.011      -3 1.204
```

9999

SPUNCH
 BLANK LINE ending saturation data
 BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
 BLANK LINE ENDING ALL CASES

The corresponding output looks as follows :

```
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 1.          ;C data://A/GUIDO/SATURA3.IN
Marker card.      preceding new      EMTD data case.      ;BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 3.          ;C input data for supporting routine SATURA
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 4.          ;C Excitation test results for 3-phase transformer
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 5.          ;C      UBASE = 27 kv (RMS, equivalent phase)
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 6.          ;C      SBASE = 750/3 = 250 MVA (equivalent phase)
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 7.          ;C      Ibase = 250 / 27 = 9.26 kA
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 8.          ;C
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 9.          ;C
34567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890 ;C
Comment card.      NUMDCD = 10.         ;C      1      2      3      4      5      6
7      8
Erase all of 0 cards in the punch buffer.      ;SERASE
Request for magnetic saturation computation.      ;SATURATION
Misc. const.      5.000E+01 2.700E+01 2.500E+02 0 ;50.0      27.00      250.0      1      0
(I. V) point.      3.94200E-04      8.43000E-01      ;.3942      -3 .8430
(I. V) point.      6.11300E-04      8.99600E-01      ;.6113      -3 .8996
(I. V) point.      8.88800E-04      9.49600E-01      ;.8888      -3 .9496
(I. V) point.      1.25300E-03      1.00000E+00      ;1.253      -3 1.0
(I. V) point.      1.48000E-03      1.01900E+00      ;1.480      -3 1.019
(I. V) point.      1.92000E-03      1.05400E+00      ;1.920      -3 1.054
(I. V) point.      2.33300E-03      1.07800E+00      ;2.333      -3 1.078
(I. V) point.      5.01100E-03      1.20400E+00      ;5.011      -3 1.204
Special termination-of-points card.      ;
9999
```

Derived saturation curve gives peak current as a function of flux :

Row	Current [amp]	Flux [volt-sec]
1	0.0000000000	0.0000000000
2	5.1618795027	102.4604983603
3	12.3418337241	109.3398153320
4	17.5040965216	115.4169504661
5	24.8062758133	121.5427026812
6	31.4592838067	123.8520140322
7	39.1754389519	128.1060086260
8	49.5865689002	131.0230334903
9	97.2627733421	146.3374140282

Next, check the derived curve by independent reverse computation. Assuming sinusoidal voltage (flux) at the level of each point.

ras current is found numerically. This curve should be equal to the original I-V points inputted.

Row	Current in P.U.	Voltage in P.U.
2	0.00039420	0.84300000
3	0.00061130	0.89960000
4	0.00088880	0.94960000
5	0.00125300	1.00000000
6	0.00148000	1.01900000
7	0.00192000	1.05400000
8	0.00233300	1.07800000
9	0.00501100	1.20400000

Request for flushing of punch buffer. ;SPUNCH

A listing of 80-column card images now being flushed from punch buffer follows.

```
*****
123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789
*****
C <++++> Cards punched by support routine on 29-Jun-89 09.04.57 <++++>
C SATURATION
C 50.0      27.00      250.0      1      0
C .3942      -3 .8430
C .6113      -3 .8996
```

631

```

C .8888      -3 .9496
C 1.253      -3 1.0
C 1.480      -3 1.019
C 1.920      -3 1.054
C 2.333      -3 1.078
C 5.011      -3 1.204
C
          9999
5.16187950E+00  1.02460498E+02
1.23418337E+01  1.09339815E+02
1.75040965E+01  1.15416950E+02
2.48062758E+01  1.21542703E+02
3.14592838E+01  1.23852014E+02
3.91754390E+01  1.28106009E+02
4.95865689E+01  1.31023033E+02
9.72627733E+01  1.46337414E+02
          9999

```

*****< End of LUNIT7 punched cards as flushed by SPUNCH request >*****

The resulting (ψ, i) characteristic looks as follows :

After the flux $\psi(t)$ exceeds saturation flux ψ_s , the last slope of the non-linearity is determined by the air-core inductance L_{air} (the additional flux travels in air).

The air-core inductance L_{air} can be approximated by the geometry of the corresponding winding (in this case the low voltage winding).

$$L_{air} \approx \mu_0 \cdot w^2 \cdot A / l$$

where A = cross-sectional area of the winding (17,925 cm²)
 l = winding length leg length (263 cm)
 w = number of turns (54)
 μ_0 = permeability of free space ($1.256637 \cdot 10^{-8}$ H/cm)

For the transformer considered, $L_{air} \approx 0.0025$ H.
 This value includes the leakage impedance of the low voltage winding. If we use the BCTRAN Matrix for the linear transformer model, the nonlinear elements are connected to the low voltage transformer terminals in addition to the linear transformer elements. (In this case it is not necessary to correct L_{air} by the winding leakage inductance) (By using the [A] [R] Matrix without excitation information, it is also not necessary to correct the nonlinear inductance elements by the linear magnetizing reactance).

For the transformer in question $\psi_s = 1.2\psi_r = 146Vs$.
 If $\psi_{as} = 0.6\psi_r = 72.9Vs$ in one leg, the flux in this winding at its first maximum becomes : $2 * 121.54 Vs + 0.6 * 121.54 Vs = 316 Vs$.
 The air flux $\psi_{air} = 316 Vs - 146 Vs = 170 Vs$.
 The last point of the nonlinear characteristic can be calculated from :

$$\Delta I_{mw} = 170 Vs / 0.0025 H : 68000 A$$

$$I_{mw} = 68000 A + 97 A = 68097 A$$

XIX-H. "HYSDAT" to create type-96 hysteretic inductor characteristic

XIX-H-1. Purpose and applications

The specification of remanent magnetism requires a (flux-current) hysteresis curve. Recall that the shape of the hysteresis loop for an inductor depends primarily on the material of the core, while the scaling of the hysteresis loop depends on geometry, the number of turns and other construction factors.

What is actually stored in supporting routine HYSDAT is essentially the shape of the loop for a certain type of material. The user then should provide information for the actual reactor being specified, so that a correct scaling can be performed. Hence the data entry is very simple.

The punched results (ψ, i) can be used for the type-96 hysteretic inductor (section V-D). Up to now, only one curve shape (corresponding to ARMCO Mn) can be selected. With some care, supporting routine SATURA (section XIX-G) can be used to generate hysteresis loops for other materials, it should be noted.

XIX-H-2. Input data deck structure for HYSDAT

In general, an input data deck for supporting routine HYSDAT has the following structure :

1. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
2. HYSTERESIS - special request to activate supporting routine HYSDAT
(see section II-A-45).
3. \$ERASE - request (optional) to clear punch buffer
4. shape specification card
5. scale specification card
6. \$PUNCH - request (optional) to activate punching.
Remark that the points 4 through 6 may be repeated as many times as desired. Each such grouping then is considered as a separate data case, corresponding to a different hysteresis loop.
7. BLANK CARD ending all hysteresis loops
8. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
9. BLANK CARD ending all cases

For an example of such input, the reader is referred to benchmark 13 (third subcase). Only card 4 and 5 deserve a further explanation. All other cards are self-explanatory.

Card 4. Shape specification card :

Since the shape of the hysteresis loop for an inductor depends primarily on the material of the core, such core material specification should be possible. This can be obtained using following card format :

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
ITYPE	LEVEL							
18	18							

Parameters:

ITYPE: type code specifying the magnetic core material of the inductor.
 = 1: ARMC0 Mh oriented silicon steel
 (perhaps, other alternatives will be provided later).

LEVEL: flag, specifying the desired level of accuracy.
 = 1: hysteresis loop represented in 4 to 5 points
 = 2: hysteresis loop represented in 10 points
 = 3: hysteresis loop represented in 15 points
 = 4: hysteresis loop represented in 20 to 25 points.

Card 5. Scale specification card :

The scaling of the hysteresis loop depends on the geometry, the number of turns and other factors of the actual construction. This scaling can be fully specified via the location of the positive saturation point. By definition, this is the point in the first quadrant where the hysteresis loop changes from being multivalued to being single-valued. Following card format allows you to specify this point :

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
CURSAT	FLXSAT							
88.0	88.0							

Parameters:

CURSAT: current (in A) of the positive saturation point.
 FLXSAT: flux (in Vs) of the positive saturation point.

Note: By definition, the positive saturation point is the point of the first quadrant where the hysteresis loop changes from being multivalued to being single-valued. One suggested way of determining values for both these coordinates from normal or DC magnetizing curves is as follows. Beginning at the right (i.e. linear part) on the normal magnetization curve, a straight-edge is used to extrapolate this line back to the left. The point where this straight line and the actual curve first begin to diverge is then taken as the positive saturation point. It is recommended to use the DC magnetization curve, since this is more readily available than hysteresis loops.

XIX-H-3. Example

The following is an extract from DC13. The input looks as follows :

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
HYSTERESIS
C ITYPE LEVEL ( Request Armco M4 oriented silicon steel -- only 1 available
  1 2 ( That was ITYPE=1. As for LEVEL=2, moderate accuracy output
  500. 1.0 ( Current and flux coordinates of positive saturation point
SPUNCH
BLANK card ending "HYSTERESIS" data cases
    
```

The output looks as follows :

```

Comment card.  -NUMDCS = 1.
Marker card preceding new DMTF data case.
Request to make Type-96 hysteresis branch cards.
Comment card.  NUMDCS = 4.
Begin 8-h generator.  ITYPE = 1.  LEVEL = 2.
CURSAT.  FLXSAT = 5.0000E+02  1.0000E+00
Derived characteristic for Type-96 pseudo-nonlinear DMTF branch card follows.
Current      Flux
-1.25000000E-02 -9.70588235E-01
-1.56250000E-01 -9.19411765E-01
9.37500000E-00 -8.47058824E-01
2.18750000E+01 -6.58823529E-01
4.21875000E+01  5.70588235E-01
C data://A/GUI00/MYS.IN
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
HYSTERESIS
C ITYPE LEVEL ( Request Armco M4 oriented silicon steel -- only 1 available
  1 2 ( That was ITYPE=1. As for LEVEL=2, moderate accuracy output
  500. 1.0 ( Current and flux coordinates of positive saturation point
    
```

6.56250000E+01 7.52941176E-01
1.12500000E+02 8.64705882E-01
2.07812500E+02 9.41176471E-01
5.00000000E+02 1.00000000E+00
6.87500000E+02 1.00588235E+00
9999.

Request for flushing of punch buffer. SPUNCH

A listing of 80-column card images now being flushed from punch buffer follows.

123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789

C <*****> Cards punched by support routine on 29-Jun-89 06.33.56 <*****>

C HYSTERESIS
C C ITYPE LEVEL (Request Arcco M4 oriented silicon steel -- only 1 availab
C 1 2 (That was ITYPE=1. As for LEVEL=2. moderate accuracy outp
C 500. 1.0 (Current and flux coordinates of positive saturation poi
-1.25000000E+02 -9.70588235E-01
-1.56250000E+01 -9.19411765E-01
9.37500000E+00 -8.47058824E-01
2.18750000E+01 -6.58823529E-01
4.21875000E+01 5.70588235E-01
6.56250000E+01 7.52941176E-01
1.12500000E+02 8.64705882E-01
2.07812500E+02 9.41176471E-01
5.00000000E+02 1.00000000E+00
6.87500000E+02 1.00588235E+00
9999.

-----< End of LUNIT7 punched cards as flushed by SPUNCH request >-----

XIX-I. "ARRDAT" to Punch Type-92 Branch Cards for ZnO Surge Arresters

Access to the supporting program "ARRDAT" is by means of a "ZNO FITTER" request of Section II-A-40. "ARRDAT" will produce the Type-92 branch cards to represent a ZnO surge arrester. In summary, "ARRDAT" accepts manufacturer's data for the surge arrester as input, and calculates parameters that are required for the Type-92 EMTP branch cards of Section V-E.

"ARRDAT" fits exponential curves to a set of data points. The fitting is performed in the log-log plane using the least-squares approach. There are two options for the determination of the number of exponential segments that are to be used. First, the user may specify the number of segments, and the boundaries of the segments. Alternatively (and more commonly), the program can determine the segments automatically, based on the maximum permissible relative error specified by the user.

An optional "BRANCH" card allows the user to name the terminal nodes for the Type-92 branch cards that will be punched. The format is identical to that used for transmission lines ("JMARTI SETUP", etc.). The user punches the request word "BRANCH" in columns 1-6, and follows this with 2A6 terminal pair names beginning in column 9. If present, such a card precedes other ZnO data cards. Refer to Section XVII for more details, if this is unclear.

Card Number 1:

C	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
C	3456789012	345678901234	567890123456	789012345678	901234567890	123456789012	
C	I12	I12	E12.0	I12	E12.0	E12.0	
C	NEXP	IPHASE	ERRLIM	IPRZNO	VREF	VFLASH	

NEXP (cols. 1-12) chooses between the two possible fitting options. A negative integer represents a request for the automatic determination of the exponential segments. Alternatively, a positive integer NUM means that the user wants this number of segments, and will be specifying the boundaries of each manually.

IPHASE (cols. 13-24) specifies the number of phases of the arrester bank for which branch cards are to be produced. If left blank or keyed with zero, the value will be changed to unity, meaning that a single arrester is to be modeled.

ERRLIM (cols. 25-36) is the maximum relative error permitted during the automatic determination of the number of segments (assuming that the user has keyed NEXP negative). A blank or zero field will be converted to the default value of 1/20. The relative error is: $ERROR = \frac{ABS(C1 - C2)}{C1}$, by definition, where C1 is the value of the current as specified by the user, and C2 is the value of the current as predicted by the exponential approximation.

IPRZNO (cols. 37-48) controls diagnostic printout. Suggested values are between zero and three. The amount of printout increases with the variable value.

VREF (cols. 49-60) is the reference voltage that will be used to scale the voltage data points. Scaling must be used to prevent numerical overflow during the subsequent EMTP simulation. The idea is to produce numbers close to unity for computer library functions. If left blank or keyed with zero, the value will be changed to twice A2 of card number 2 immediately below.

VFLASH (cols. 61-72) is the gap flashover voltage in units of [volts]. This is peak value, not RMS (effective). Leave this field blank, or key with zero if the arrester is gapless.

The interpretation of this input data card confirms values for variables NEXP, IPHASE, IPRZNO, VREF, and VFLASH, in that order, encoded using format (3I4, 2E12.3). An example follows the explanation of the (I, V) characteristic below.

Card Number 2:

C	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
C	3456789012	345678901234	567890123456	789012345678	901234567890	123456789012	
C	E12.0	E12.0	E12.0	E12.0	E12.0	E12.0	E12.0
C	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	AMIN	

A1 (cols. 1-12) is the voltage rating of the arrester upon which the input data are based. This is in units of [volts] RMS.

A2 (cols. 13-24) is the desired voltage rating of the arrester in units of [volts] RMS. This really is just a scaling factor, so it can be used creatively in more than one way by the user. For example, A2 can be used to convert the arrester input data (the voltages) from per unit to [volts]. Alternatively, the user could produce the characteristic of an electrically similar arrester having a different voltage rating. The properties of similar arresters do not change with rating, provided a proportional number of blocks is used to obtain the new rating. Note that if VREF is maintained proportional to A2, then similar arresters will have identical parameters at all ratings.

A3 (cols. 25-36) is a multiplier used for the additional scaling of voltage points. For example, it can be used to obtain a minimum characteristic (maximum energy) from a maximum characteristic (maximum voltage). The most commonly used value is unity, however.

A4 (cols. 37-48) is a current multiplier that is used to obtain results for arresters with number of columns that differ from that for which the data points are known. An even current distribution is assumed.

A5 (cols. 49-60) is a flag signaling the existence (or lack of it) of additional data describing the arrester after flashover of the arrester gap. This parameter permits the representation of two different situations. First, arresters with shunt, passive gaps. The shunted portion of the arrester can be of similar, or dissimilar, material, in this case. Second, arresters with series, passive gaps. Before gap flashover, the arrester is inoperative. Therefore, this data specifies the actual nonlinear material characteristic. By means of his A5 value, the user chooses among these: a) If zero or unity, the arrester is gapless, and no additional data follows; b) If negative, additional data follows (to represent dissimilar material for a shunt or a series gap); c) If positive but not unity, there is no further data. Instead, the original input data are to be used after multiplication of the voltages by A5.

AMIN (cols. 61-72) is the minimum current above which segment number one of the arrester characteristic begins. Even if fitting a straight line that passes through the origin, do not leave AMIN blank or zero, since the logarithm of zero is not defined.

The interpretation of this card confirms values for variables A1, A2, A3, and A4, in that order, encoded using format (4E10.2). An example follows the explanation of the (I, V) characteristic immediately below.

Cards that Specify the Arrester Characteristic

Cards that specify the arrester characteristic come next. For the most common case of NEXP (see Card 1) negative, the program automatically determines the segments, and there is to be only one data group. But for positive NEXP, there are to be NEXP groups of data. Within any one group, current and voltage pairs defining the characteristic are to be keyed with one point per card, as follows:

C	1	2
C	3456789012	345678901234
C	E12.0	E12.0
C	CURRENT	VOLTAGE

Points must be in order of increasing current and voltage. Each such group is to be terminated by a blank card. The interpretation will confirm the (I, V) point, of course, as well as its number in order of input (see next paragraph).

All "ZNO FITTER" data cases will involve all data cards explained thus far, with the possible exception of the optional "BRANCH" card. Hence, with no loss of generality, the interpretation of all of them can be shown together. The following comes from the start of the solution to the first subcase of BENCHMARK DC-39:

```

C      1      2      3      4      5      6      7
C 3456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456
C -----
Request to generate Type-92 ZnO branch cards.          ZNO FITTER (Special-r
6 pairs of bus names for next 6 phases.              BRANCH RECA          RECB
Arrester.      1  3  0  4.125E+05  3.800E+05          1          3
Ratings.      7.07E+02  1.92E+05  9.62E-01  3.00E+00          707.107  192000.
(I,V) point 1.  1.000000E+00  1.164800E+03          1.0  1164.8
<<  Etc. (10 lines, for points 2 through 11, removed to save space)  >>
(I,V) point 12.  3.000000E+03  1.556800E+03          3000.  1556.8
Blank card terminates ZnO characteristic.             BLANK card bounds points
    
```

If and only if parameter A5 of data card number 2 is less than zero, and VFLASH of card number 1 was greater than zero, then two additional items of information must be supplied to define the ZnO characteristic after flashover. First, there is to be another card number 1, although only variable NEXP of columns 1-12 will actually be read from the card (all other parameters of the card are assumed to remain unchanged). This gives the user the opportunity to change his fitting option for the flashover characteristic. Second, there are to be cards specifying the arrester characteristic after flashover. The (CURRENT, VOLTAGE) pairs, indeterminate in number and terminated by a blank card, have the same format as previously described.

Stacking of ZnO Data Cases; Termination; Punched Cards

An indeterminate number of data cases can be stacked sequentially and solved in a single execution by the program. Each new case follows immediately the blank card terminating the data for the last segment of the preceding case. After the last such ZnO data case, one extra blank card then exits the supporting program "ARRDAT".

As with other supporting programs, SPUNCH is used to create the Type-92 branch cards that represent the ZnO arrester being processed. If the user wants such output, it is his responsibility to request it. The punched output is particularly valuable because it includes comment cards that label the Type-92 branch parameters. As an example, consider the punched output from the solution to the first subcase of BENCHMARK DC-39:

A listing of 80-column card images now being flushed from punch buffer follows.

```

=====
1234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890
=====
C Rating = 192000.0  V-mult = 9.62000E-01  I-mult = 3.00000E+00  Capless
92RECA          5555.
C          V-reference          V-flashover
  4.125000000000000000000E+05  9.2121212121212130E-01
C          Multiplier          Exponent          V-min
  2.9479544296115170E+04  2.6530262418533470E+01  5.4505063612285050E-01
          9999
  5.9605957177725360E+05  2.6530262418533470E+01  4.8665227581674000E-01
          9999
92RECB          RECA          5555.
92RECC          RECA          5555.
    
```

Illustrative Usage: The data of BENCHMARK DC-39

Consider a single-column ZnO arrester. The voltage points are known for an arrester rated 1-KV (crest), maximum voltage characteristic. The current points are given in [amperes] (crest). The user wants parameters for a 192-KV (rms), 3-column arrester with a maximum energy characteristic. The conversion factor to this characteristic is 0.962, by assumption. The arrester is equipped with a shunt gap, and the shunted part is electrically similar to the rest of the arrester. The shunt gap consists of 12% additional blocks. That is, after gap sparkover, the arrester contains 0.89286 ($1 / 1.12 = 0.89286$) of the original blocks, from which it follows that $A5 = 0.89286$. A reference voltage equal to 412.5 KV was chosen, since this is the expected operating range of the 3-phase surge arrester. Finally, the arrester is assumed to be equipped with a shunt gap that flashes over at 380 KV (crest). For this basic data, three different EMTP representations are to be obtained, as summarized in the following three subsections. This information was used to construct BENCHMARK DC-39, so the user is referred to this standard test case to see the EMTP implementation.

1) DC-39 subcase 1: Single-Exponent Fit (NEXP = 1)

According to the data provided above, the following values are assigned: 1) $A1 = 1000 / 1.414$ is the original rating of the arrester in [volts] (rms); 2) $A2 = 192000$ is the desired rating of the output in [volts] (rms); 3) $A3 = 0.962$ is the scaling factor for obtaining the desired maximum energy characteristic; 4) $A4 = 3.0$ since the original data are given for a single-column arrester, this factor of three will convert them to the desired 3-column device; 5) $A5 = 0.89286$ since the arrester before flashover contains 12% additional blocks; 6) $AMIN = 1.E-3$ [amperes] would be a common default choice, which is about the end of the leakage current region.

2) DC-39 subcase 2: Double Exponential Fit (NEXP = 2)

Next, the characteristic described above is to be fitted with two exponentials. The border between the two segments has been determined graphically using log-log paper to lie between 100A and 200A. All other parameters on cards number 1 and number 2 remain unchanged.

3) DC-39 subcase 3: Automatic Segment Determination (NEXP = -1)

Finally, the same data will be fitted with a relative current error of $1/20$, which means that $ERRLIM = 1/20$.

XIX-J. Convert saturable transformer cards to linear equivalent [R],[L]

This supporting routine can be used to convert data lines for the SATURABLE TRANSFORMER model (IV.E) into a coupled [R],[L] equivalent (type 51,52,53 branches).

The user should be carefull, however, because some inherent limitations exist for the conversion routine:

- Although the SATURABLE TRANSFORMER component can take non-linear behaviour into account, the type 51,52,53 equivalent branches can not: they only provide a LINEAR equivalent. Of course, the user can add the non-linear behaviour as an external branch, but this is tricky (zero magnetizing current is not honored).
- Although the SATURABLE TRANSFORMER component can process transformers with zero magnetizing current, type 51,52,53 can not. This situation is similar to the XFORMER model. Recall that only the BCTRAN model can process zero magnetizing current, because it has the AR-notation available.
- The data lines for the SATURABLE TRANSFORMER model should be self-contained (i.e. no reference component usage that copies the data of a preceding transformer).
- For the ATP4 version, the punched output is not immediately usable because the free-format output form is incorrect with respect to the node names: the user himself should add separating commas inbetween the fields of the node names. Please refer to punched cards of this model with XFORMER punched cards for comparison. This is a bug that has to be cleared in next program releases (see section J.4).

XIX-J.1. Input data deck structure:

Suppose a user wants to convert a self-contained (i.e. no reference branch usage) SATURABLE TRANSFORMER dataset into a linear equivalent [R],[L]-notation. For that reason he would use the supporting routine "CHANGE TRANSFORMER". The input data deck would look as follows:

- 1) BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
- 2) CHANGE TRANSFORMER
- 3) \$ERASE
- 4) self-contained SATURABLE TRANSFORMER data case
 remark: - no reference component usage allowed
 - no zero magnetizing current allowed
 - specification of non-linear characteristic will not be taken into account in the final linear model.
- 5) BLANK card ending CHANGE TRANSFORMER supporting routine
- 6) \$PUNCH
- 7) BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
- 8) BLANK CARD ENDING ALL CASES

Remark that several point-4 data may be stacked one after the other, without the need to separate. For an example, we refer to the first subcase of DC67.

The card formats to be used are so obvious that they do not need to be explained.

XIX-J.2. Example

Following example is an extract of benchmark DC-67, where only the first subcase is used.

```
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
CHANGE TRANSFORMER { Special-request word transfers to special conversion code
$ERASE { Rewind (erase) buffer of punched cards as we prepare to punch more
TRANSFORMER .005 30. TRANFF 1.E4 3
.005 30. { 1st point of (current, flux): characteristic
.01 40. { 2nd point of (current, flux): characteristic
.02 45. { 3rd point ...
0.1 50. { 4th point ...
5.0 100. { 5th and final point of (current, flux) char.
```

```

          9999      { Special terminator bounds characteristic (current = 9999)
1GENT OPEN          5.0 5.E4 50.          { 1st of 2 winding cards
2LOADOFF           20. 2.E5 100.         { 2nd and final winding card
          BLANK card ends saturable TRANSFORMER components to be converted to [R], [L].
$PUNCH             { Flush the punched-card output of just-created Type-51, 52, ...
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
BLANK

```

XIX-J.3. Output data deck structure:

```

A listing of 80-column card images now being flushed from punch buffer follows.
=====
1234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789
=====
C <++++++> Cards punched by support routine on 29-Jan-91 16.20.46 <++++++>
C CHANGE TRANSFORMER { Special-request word transfers to special conversion code
C $ERASE             { Rewind (erase) buffer of punched cards as we prepare to punch more
C TRANSFORMER       .005 30.TRANFF 1.E4
C                   .005 30. { 1st point of (current, flux): characterist
C                   .01 40. { 2nd point of (current, flux): characterist
C                   .02 45. { 3rd point ...
C                   0.1 50. { 4th point ...
C                   5.0 100. { 5th and final point of (current, flux) char.
C                   9999 { Special terminator bounds characteristic (current = 9999)
C 1GENT OPEN        5.0 5.E4 50.          { 1st of 2 winding cards
C 2LOADFF          20. 2.E5 100.         { 2nd and final winding card
51GENT OPEN        5.9066393442623E+03 , 1.2795081967213E+06 , , , ,
52LOADFF          1.1803278688525E+04 , 2.4590163934426E+06 $
                   2.3626557377049E+04 , 5.1180327868852E+06 , , , ,
=====
=====< End of LUNIT7 punched cards as flushed by $PUNCH request >=====

```

Note that the output is not in the legal free format: no separation by comma's in between node names. Following section shows how data should be modified.

XIX-J.4. Usage

The first case is the representation of the saturable transformer as it appears in its normal form:

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
$WIDTH, 79, { Request narrow, 80-column LUNIT6 output as an illustration
BEGIN PEAK VALUE SEARCH, -1, { Time of -1 is request to read following card
  0.5 1.5 2.5 3.5 { Limit extrema to these 2 subranges
PRINTED NUMBER WIDTH, 10, 2, { Request max precision of 6 numbers in 80 bytes
 .010 6.0
  1 1 1 1 1 -1
  5 5 20 100 100
GEN GENT 1.E-3 3
LOADFF 1.0E0 3
TRANSFORMER .005 30.TRANFF 1.E4
 .005 30.
 .01 40.
 .02 45.
 0.1 50.
 5.0 100.
 9999
1GENT OPEN 5.0 5.E4 50.
2LOADFF 20. 2.E5 100.
 OPEN 1.E7
BLANK card finishing all branch cards
BLANK card ending non-existent switch cards
14GEN 200. .1591549 -1.
BLANK card terminating program source cards
 1 { Request for all node voltage outputs
C PRINTER PLOT
C 193 .5 0.0 4.0 LOAD GEN GENT
BLANK card terminating plot cards
$WIDTH, 132, { Done with 80 columns, so return to wide, 132-column LUNIT6 output
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
BLANK

```

The next case will show the same example, but now in the [R],[L] representation, with use of the punched card. There is a necessary manual manipulation needed, because of program bug.

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
$WIDTH, 79, { Request narrow, 80-column LUNIT6 output as an illustration
BEGIN PEAK VALUE SEARCH, -1, { Time of -1 is request to read following card
  0.5 1.5 2.5 3.5 { Limit extrema to these 2 subranges
PRINTED NUMBER WIDTH, 10, 2, { Request max precision of 6 numbers in 80 bytes
 .010 6.0
  1 1 1 1 1 -1
  5 5 20 100 100
GEN GENT 1.E-3 3
LOADFF 1.0E3 3
C 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

```

```

C 34567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890
51,GENT,OPEN,,,          5.9066393442623E+03,1.2795081967213E+06,,,,, {remark extra comma's
52,LOADFF,,,            1.1803278688525E+04,2.4590163934426E+06$ {following type code and
                                2.3626557377049E+04,5.1180327868852E+06,,,,, {node names
OPEN
1.E7
BLANK card finishing all branch cards
BLANK card ending non-existent switch cards
14GEN          70. .1591549          -1.
BLANK card terminating program source cards
1 { Request for all node voltage outputs
C PRINTER PLOT
C 193 .5 0.0 4.0          LOADFF          GEN          GENT
BLANK card terminating plot cards
$WIDTH, 132, { Done with 80 columns, so return to wide, 132-column LUNIT6 output
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
BLANK

```